

User Guide: UKCP Threshold Detector for Decision-Relevant Climate Information

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1. Background

The Threshold Detector project, delivered under the Met Office Hadley Centre Climate Programme, has created a user-informed capability to explore crossings of decision-relevant thresholds in climate data.

Climate impacts and adaptation decisions often depend not on changes in mean conditions, but on the frequency of threshold crossings - for example, how often critical temperatures, rainfall totals, or wind speeds are surpassed or not reached. Stakeholders across sectors have highlighted the need for a Threshold Detector tool to provide this information. For example, transport operators may need information on high-temperature exceedances that affect roads or railways, energy providers may be interested in wind speed thresholds relevant for turbine operation, and agricultural users may consider temperature thresholds linked to crop phenology. In response, the tool described in this document has been developed, tested and disseminated as a code base via a GitHub repository. Its development was informed by a stakeholder engagement workshop held online on 28 January 2026, and the resulting capability aims to support government priorities on climate resilience and adaptation.

The Threshold Detector code is available on GitHub and can be accessed at:

https://github.com/MetOffice/ukcp_threshold_detector

2. Introduction

This section introduces the Threshold Detector. When using the tool, users are encouraged to follow the good practice guidance provided in Section 6.

The Threshold Detector analyses gridded daily data to compute threshold-crossing metrics, including crossing counts, number of spells, and maximum spell length, for the variables:

- *tasmax* (maximum air temperature)
- *tasmin* (minimum air temperature)
- *tas* (mean air temperature)
- *pr* (precipitation rain)
- *uas* (eastward wind component)
- *vas* (northward wind component)
- *sfcWind* (wind speed at 10 m)
- *hurs* (relative humidity)
- *huss* (specific humidity)
- *prsn* (snowfall flux)

Only the variables listed above have been included, as these have been tested in greater

detail. However, the code is designed to operate on any input provided in a spatio-temporal grid format, meaning that additional variables can be incorporated through minor adaptations to the code if required.

The tool uses the Python library *xarray* (tested with version 2025.11) to read and analyse the input data provided in NetCDF format. A full environment specification, including versions of all major dependencies, is provided in the *environment.yml* file.. Users may also save the output as a NetCDF file. Additional functionality to convert NetCDF output to raster GeoTiff (.tif) format is provided to aid GIS applications. The output field retains the same attributes as the input and includes a coordinate, *year*, which represents the time dimension giving the threshold-crossing metric for each analysed year. While the Detector was developed for application to UK Climate Projections (UKCP18) gridded data [1] across different spatial resolutions, it has been designed generically so that its core threshold-crossing computations can operate seamlessly on any suitably gridded dataset. The code has therefore also been tested and applied to HadUK-Grid observational data [2], which are supported as valid inputs to the tool. Other datasets may also be used (for example, alternative regional or global climate model output, or observational and reanalysis products), although caution is advised, as certain peripheral functionalities, particularly those dependent on the coordinate system and the prescribed spatial coordinates, may not operate as intended if the input differs from the UKCP18 standard specifications (e.g. map visualisations or file conversion to a GIS-compatible format). Users applying the Detector to alternative datasets may therefore need to make dataset-specific adaptations to ensure compatibility with certain visualisation and GIS-export functionalities. The tool returns gridded fields of threshold crossings as its main output and can also generate simple visual products, such as maps of annual exceedances over a specified period, or time series of area-mean threshold-crossing metrics.

To ensure scalability, the Threshold Detector has been tested across datasets with varying spatial resolutions, demonstrating its capacity to operate consistently across different spatial scales. While analyses at 12 km resolution allow faster computations that typically complete within seconds, users may require the greater spatial detail provided by higher-resolution datasets (e.g. 2.2 km or 1 km), albeit at increased computational cost. Working with such datasets therefore requires additional computing resources. Even so, analyses can generally be completed within minutes rather than seconds, thereby maintaining practical timeliness for most applications. Where resources are more constrained, data may be processed in segments, for example, by analysing one decade at a time rather than all available years within a single run. The tool supports this approach by allowing users to select and analyse subsets of the available years independently. Any subsequent combination or aggregation of outputs across subsets is left to the user and will depend on the intended application.

The GitHub repository *ukcp_threshold_detector* contains the code that delivers the Threshold Detector capability, together with brief installation instructions, accompanying documentation and illustrative examples of its functionality. A more detailed user guide is presented in this document. Section 3 outlines the code structure, including guidance on input data preparation and an overview of the modules and their components. Although the

tool was primarily developed for univariate analyses (single-variable threshold crossings), it also supports analyses of simple compound events defined as the concurrent crossing of two thresholds corresponding to two different variables, as described in Section 4. Section 5 presents a number of application examples, and Section 6 concludes with guidance on good practice.

3. Code Structure

3.1. Overview

The Python libraries required by the Threshold Detector are *xarray*, *glob*, *numpy*, *matplotlib*, *pyproj*, *cartopy*, and *rasterio*, and their dependencies. An *environment.yml* file is provided to help users set up a tested environment with the required dependencies. A schematic illustration of the tool is shown in Figure 1. The tool is built around a high-level class called *ThresholdDetector*, with which users can create a detection instance by specifying the variable of interest, the threshold, and the crossing method (going above or below the threshold). Optionally, they may also specify the ensemble member (i.e. an individual model simulation within the UKCP ensemble), or indicate that observations should be used for the analysis instead of UKCP data. Once an instance is created, which holds all the high-level information, users can apply it to multiple functions (called methods in Python) without the need to re-specify the high-level information (variable, threshold, crossing method) each time. The same instance can be used to call different methods as required. The tool currently includes three methods that compute three different detection metrics (threshold-crossing counts, number of spells, and maximum spell length), as well as two additional methods for basic visualisation of the computed metrics. The different code components are represented by the blue boxes in Figure 1 and are described in Section 3.3. Additional utility functions and capabilities are listed in Section 3.4. Before detailing the individual modules and methods, data preparation is first outlined in Section 3.2.

3.2. Data preparation

Before running a threshold detection, users must specify the paths to the input data by editing the file *input_datapaths.py*. The NetCDF files containing daily gridded data should be stored in separate folders for each variable and each UKCP18 ensemble member (or for each variable when HadUK-Grid data is used instead). Each folder should contain only the relevant NetCDF input files.

The data may be stored in a single file or split across multiple files. The code accepts any number of files and any file naming convention, and will loop through all available NetCDF files in the folder to determine which dates each file contains.

Figure 1. The structure of the Threshold Detector.

The file *input_datapaths.py* contains a Python dictionary that maps data paths to specific variables and ensemble members. An example of the dictionary format is shown below:

```

inputs = {
    'tasmax_obs' : '/data/users/username/haduk_grid/12km/tasmax/',
    'tasmin_obs' : '/data/users/username/haduk_grid/12km/tasmin/',
    'pr_obs' : '/data/users/username/haduk_grid/12km/rainfall/',

    'tasmax_01' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/tasmax/01/',
    'tasmin_01' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/tasmin/01/',
    'tas_01' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/tas/01/',
    'pr_01' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/pr/01/',
    'uas_01' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/uas/01/',
    'vas_01' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/vas/01/',
    'sfcWind_01' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/sfcWind/01/',
    'hurs_01' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/hurs/01/',
    'huss_01' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/huss/01/',
    'prsn_01' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/prsn/01/',

    'tasmax_04' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/tasmax/04/',
    'tasmin_04' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/tasmin/04/',
    'tas_04' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/tas/04/',
    'pr_04' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/pr/04/',
    'uas_04' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/uas/04/',
    'vas_04' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/vas/04/',
    'sfcWind_04' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/sfcWind/04/',
    'hurs_04' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/hurs/04/',
    'huss_04' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/huss/04/',
    'prsn_04' : '/data/users/username/ukcp18/uk_12km_rcp85/prsn/04/',
}
    
```

In the example above, the user provides the paths for three variables from HadUK-Grid and ten variables for UKCP18 ensemble members 1 and 4. The file can be edited to add or remove variables and/or ensemble members as required. The paths are mapped to names that follow the naming convention *var_X*, where *var* denotes the variable name and *X* is either the two-digit ensemble member ID for UKCP18 data or *obs* for HadUK-Grid data.

3.3. Module `analysis.py`

Module `analysis.py` contains the main code of the tool and defines the class `ThresholdDetector`. The class stores information about the detection setup and provides methods to compute threshold-crossing metrics and generate simple plots of the results. The tool's capabilities are described within the code comments and are also summarised briefly below. Illustrative examples of how these are used are provided in Section 5.

- **Class `ThresholdDetector`.** This is the basic building block of the tool and the starting point of all computations, which are performed using a set of methods defined within the class.
 - Class Inputs:
 - **var:** input variable - can be one of `'tasmax'`, `'tasmin'`, `'tas'`, `'pr'`, `'uas'`, `'vas'`, `'sfcWind'`, `'hurs'`, `'huss'`, `'prsn'`
 - **threshold:** threshold value
 - **ens** (optional): an integer indicating the ensemble member (default = 1)
 - **obs** (optional): True if analysing HadUK-Grid observations (default = False)
 - **method** (optional): threshold crossing method - can be `'above'` (default) or `'below'`. The threshold represents the limiting value, and only values strictly above/below it are counted as crossings.
 - Class Attributes (information created and stored in the instance):
 - **var:** input variable
 - **threshold:** threshold value
 - **ens:** ensemble member
 - **method:** threshold crossing method
 - **indata:** directory where the input files (NetCDF - daily data) are stored

The methods of the `ThresholdDetector` that compute threshold-crossing metrics are:

- **Method `detect`.** This is the most basic threshold-crossing function that computes the number of days the threshold is crossed in each year. It takes as an input an instance of the `ThresholdDetector` and, optionally, the following parameters:
 - **select_years:** a list of years to analyse. This is useful for high-resolution data, where analysing smaller segments helps avoid memory limitations.
 - **select_months:** a list of months to analyse. Months are specified numerically (e.g. June-July-August would be [6, 7, 8]). If None (default) then annual exceedances are computed. This is a useful option if, for example, users want to

calculate exceedances in a season. Note that *select_months* allows selection of any subset of months, whether contiguous or not. For example, selecting December-January-February would return valid results although not for a standard winter season, unless *years_from_dec* (defined next) is specified.

- **years_from_dec**: if set to True, then years run from Dec to Nov instead of the default Jan to Dec (so, for example, 2026 corresponds to Dec 2025-Nov 2026). This option allows users to select year-long periods that align with full meteorological seasons, and, in combination with *select_months*, to analyse threshold crossings in any season.
- **output_file**: name of a NetCDF file to save the output.
- **Method detect_maxlength**. This method computes the maximum spell length in each year, where spells are defined as consecutive days above (or below) the threshold. The method has the same input parameters as method detect.
- **Method detect_spells**. This method computes the total number of threshold-crossing spells in each year. Spells are again defined as consecutive days above (or below) the threshold. Spells of a minimum length (*min_length*) may be specified. Also, spells may be considered separate only if there are at least X non-exceedance days (*decluster_days*) between them. In addition to the input parameters of method detect, this method also includes the following (optional) parameters:
 - **min_length**: if specified, only spells with at least *min_length* days are counted.
 - **decluster_days**: minimum number of days without a threshold crossing required between spells. If set to 1 (default), all spells are counted, even if only separated by 1 day.

The output metrics are calculated only for grid cells with complete temporal coverage, and years with less than 360 days of data are excluded. These constraints ensure robust calculations by preventing the metrics from being affected by missing data.

Class *ThresholdDetector* includes two methods for basic output visualisation. These methods are designed to be applied to the UK region covered by UKCP or HadUK-Grid data and may not work correctly if the input fields have non-standard co-ordinate names or grid specifications. They are also expected to work with datasets on a standard OSGB grid (EPSG:27700), although this has not been extensively tested beyond these datasets. The visualisation methods are intended as simple convenience tools for quick visualisation and provide only limited customisation options; users requiring more advanced control over plot appearance should use standard xarray/Matplotlib functionality on the returned data.

- **Method plot_temporal_mean**. This method plots a map of the mean threshold-crossing metric over a period starting in year *y1* and ending in year *y2*. It takes as an input an instance of the *ThresholdDetector* as well as the following:
 - **var_counts**: a DataArray with the threshold-crossing metric (created by one of the detect methods)
 - **y1, y2**: the first and last years of the selected period
 - **set_label** (optional): a customised label for the plot
 - **interactive** (optional): an option to enable interactive mode (default). Setting to

- *False* ensures compatibility with environments such as VSCode
 - **output_file** (optional): name of a png file to save the plot
- **Method plot_spatial_mean.** This method plots the timeseries of the annual mean threshold-crossing metric over an area. It takes as an input an instance of the *ThresholdDetector* as well as the following:
 - **var_counts:** a DataArray with the threshold-crossing metric (created by one of the detect methods)
 - **mylon, mylat** (optional): 2-dimensional lists with the coordinates of an area to extract. If not given, the mean is computed over the entire area
 - **interactive** (optional): an option to enable interactive mode (default). Setting to *False* ensures compatibility with environments such as VSCode
 - **set_label** (optional): a customised label for the plot
 - **output_file** (optional): name of a png file to save the plot

3.4. Module `analysis_utils.py`

Module `analysis_utils.py` contains supporting functions used during detection analyses. These may be called by methods of the *ThresholdDetector* or used independently to provide additional functionality, such as file format conversions. The available functions are:

- **make_color_cmap:** a function that creates a custom colour map used for map plotting.
- **find_years_to_analyse:** a function that determines the years contained in each of the input files and selects the years to analyse.
- **find_years_to_analyse_compound:** as `find_years_to_analyse` but for analyses of compound events.
- **extract_year_data:** a function that extracts data for a specific year.
- **extract_year_data_compound:** as `extract_year_data` but for compound events.
- **cumulative_runlength:** a function that computes the run length of consecutive threshold exceedances along the time dimension.
- **make_spatial_mean:** a function that computes the weighted spatial mean of UKCP or HadUK-Grid fields for each time slice.
- **gwl_ukcp18:** a function that takes as input the threshold metric created by the detector and returns it on a selected Global Warming Level (GWL). Note that this function is to be used only for UKCP18 ensemble members, as they are the only input for which the detector knows the time slices corresponding to different GWLs [3]. The user must provide the ensemble member and GWL of interest (available levels: 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, and 4 °C).
- **nc2tif_ukcp18:** a function that converts NetCDF output from the Threshold Detector to raster (GeoTIFF) format for GIS applications. It transforms `.nc` files to `.tif`, assuming that the UKCP18 coordinate system was used. The code requires the spatial fields to be on the UKCP18 (or HadUK-Grid) coordinate system and the

coordinates to have standard names (e.g., for latitude either *projection_y_coordinate* or *grid_latitude*).

- **apply_spatial_smoothing**: a function that spatially smooths the metric created the *ThresholdDetector*. It replaces each grid-point value by the mean of the $N \times N$ grid boxes around it. Default box-size N is set to 3 (i.e. smoothing uses the mean of $3 \times 3 = 9$ values around the grid-point).

A set of unit tests for some key functions in *analysis_utils.py* are provided in folder *tests* and file **test_analysis_utils.py** and can be run using *pytest*.

4. Compound Events

In addition to univariate analyses (threshold crossings of a single variable), the *ThresholdDetector* has been extended to also support simple compound events, defined as days when the thresholds of two variables are crossed simultaneously. The compound functionality is implemented in *analysis_compound.py*, which extends the original *analysis.py* module to handle two variables and their respective thresholds. As before, a detection instance can be created using a high-level class, now called *ThresholdDetectorCompound*, which is an extension of the original *ThresholdDetector*. The class inputs and attributes for compound events are listed below:

- **Class *ThresholdDetectorCompound***. This is the basic building block of the tool for compound events.
 - Class Inputs:
 - **var**: input variables - a list of the two variables that define the compound event - acceptable variables are: *'tasmax'*, *'tasmin'*, *'tas'*, *'pr'*, *'uas'*, *'vas'*, *'sfcWind'*, *'hurs'*, *'huss'*, *'prsn'*
 - **threshold**: a list of the two threshold values
 - **method**: a list of the two threshold-crossing methods - can be *'above'* or *'below'*
 - **ens** (optional): an integer indicating the ensemble member (default = 1)
 - **obs** (optional): *True* if analysing HadUK-Grid observations (default = *False*)
 - Class Attributes:
 - **var**: input variables
 - **threshold**: threshold values
 - **ens**: ensemble member
 - **method**: threshold crossing methods
 - **indata**: directories where the input UKCP18 files (NetCDF - daily data) are stored

Once an instance is created, the tool works in the same way as in the univariate case. This means that users can compute up to three different threshold-crossing metrics with the

methods `detect`, `detect_maxlength`, `detect_spells` described in Section 3.3. The plotting methods `plot_temporal_mean` and `plot_spatial_mean` can also be used to quickly visualise the outputs.

5. Examples

5.1. Basic use

```
# Import the Detector
from analysis import ThresholdDetector

# Instantiate a detection for tasmax > 27.C
mydetection = ThresholdDetector('tasmax', 27.)

# Compute threshold crossings
thresh_metric = mydetection.detect()

# Display the dimensions of the output DataArray
# (example output for UKCP18 data)
print(thresh_metric.dims)
# ('year', 'ensemble_member',
#  'projection_y_coordinate', 'projection_x_coordinate')

# Plot a map of the mean exceedances in the 2070s
mydetection.plot_temporal_mean(thresh_metric, 2070, 2079)

# Plot the timeseries of annual threshold exceedances averaged over the area of
# Wales (-5.5 to -2.5 deg longitude, 51.4 to 53.5 deg latitude)
mydetection.plot_spatial_mean(thresh_metric, mylon = [-5.5, -2.5], mylat = [51.4,
53.5])
```

The two plots produced from the basic use example are shown in Figure 2.

5.2. Creating an instance

```
# Example 1: Max temperature above 30.C
mydetection = ThresholdDetector('tasmax', 30.)

# Example 2: Min temperature below 0.C, ensemble member 8
mydetection = ThresholdDetector('tasmin', 0., method = 'below', ens = 8)

# Example 3: Max temperature above 27.C, computed using observations
mydetection = ThresholdDetector('tasmax', 27., obs = True)
```


Figure 2. Plots from the basic use example. Map of the mean threshold exceedances in the period 2070-2079 (left) and timeseries of the threshold crossings averaged over the wider area of Wales (right).

5.3. Computing different detection metrics

```
# In the following examples an instance has been created for tasmax > 27.
mydetection = ThresholdDetector('tasmax', 27.)

# Example 1: Counts. Computes number of days when the threshold is exceeded.
thresh_metric_1 = mydetection.detect()

# Example 2: Spells. Computes number of spells in a year, i.e. consecutive days
when the threshold is exceeded. In this case spells can be of any length.
thresh_metric_2 = mydetection.detect_spells()

# Example 3: Spells. Computes number of spells in a year, but only for spells >= 5
days.
thresh_metric_3 = mydetection.detect_spells(min_length = 5)

# Example 4: Spells. As example 3, but spells separated by 3 days or less are
counted as a single event.
thresh_metric_4 = mydetection.detect_spells(min_length = 5, decluster_days = 3)

# Example 5: Max spell length. Computes the length of the longest spell of each
year.
thresh_metric_5 = mydetection.detect_maxlength()

# ADDITIONAL FUNCTIONALITY

# Basic detection
thresh_metric = mydetection.detect()
```

```
# Analyse only selected years
thresh_metric = mydetection.detect(select_years = [2070, 2071, 2072, 2073, 2074])

# Compute threshold-crossings only in summer months (June, July, August)
thresh_metric = mydetection.detect(select_months = [6, 7, 8])

# Start years in December instead of January
thresh_metric = mydetection.detect(years_from_dec = True)

# Save output in a NetCDF file
thresh_metric = mydetection.detect(output_file = 'thresh_metric.nc')
```

5.4. Visualisation

```
# Plot map of the metric over period 2020-2029 and save into a png file
mydetection.plot_temporal_mean(thresh_metric, 2020, 2029, output_file =
'plot.png')

# Add a customised label
mydetection.plot_temporal_mean(thresh_metric, 2020, 2029, set_label = 'Max Spell
Length')

# Plot timeseries of the metric averaged over the entire region and save in file
mydetection.plot_spatial_mean(thresh_metric, output_file = 'plot.png')

# Plot timeseries of the metric value averaged over the London area
mydetection.plot_spatial_mean(thresh_metric, mylon = [-0.6, 0.4], mylat = [51.2,
51.8])
```

5.5. Metrics on GWLs

```
# Import the detector and GWL functions
from analysis import ThresholdDetector
from analysis_utils import gw1_ukcp18

# Create a simple threshold metric, as in the earlier basic use example,
# for counting days with tasmax > 27.
mydetection = ThresholdDetector('tasmax', 27.)
thresh_metric = mydetection.detect()

# Compute the metric for a GWL of 2 degrees and save it in a file
thresh_metric_gwl = gw1_ukcp18(thresh_metric, ens = mydetection.ens, gw1 = 2.0,
output_file = 'thresh_2deg_gwl.nc')
```

5.6. Compound events

```
# Example compound event: hot and dry days with tasmax > 30. C and pr < 1 mm.
from analysis_compound import ThresholdDetectorCompound
mydetection = ThresholdDetectorCompound(['tasmax', 'pr'], [30., 1.], ['above',
'below'], ens=8)

# Compute three metrics: 1) crossing counts, 2) spells of three days or more in
length, 3) longest spell length
thresh_metric_1 = mydetection.detect()
thresh_metric_2 = mydetection.detect_spells(min_length = 3)
thresh_metric_3 = mydetection.detect_maxlength()

# Visualisations for thresh_metric_1
mydetection.plot_temporal_mean(thresh_metric_1, 2070, 2079)
mydetection.plot_spatial_mean(thresh_metric_1)
```

5.7. Other supporting functions

```
# Import from modules, create an instance and compute simple metric
from analysis import ThresholdDetector
from analysis_utils import nc2tif_ukcp18, apply_spatial_smoothing

mydetection = ThresholdDetector('tasmax', 30.)
thresh_metric = mydetection.detect(output_file = 'thresh_metric.nc')

# Example 1: convert output NetCDF file to GeoTiff for GIS applications
nc2tif_ukcp18('thresh_metric.nc')

# Example 2: spatially smooth field, using the mean of NxN boxes
metric_smoothed_3x3 = apply_spatial_smoothing(thresh_metric, box_size = 3)
metric_smoothed_7x7 = apply_spatial_smoothing(thresh_metric, box_size = 7)
```

6. Good Practice Guidance

The Threshold Detector allows users to explore changes in crossings of critical thresholds in a warming climate, based on state-of-the-art climate model data and scientific methods to support decision-making, for example in adaptation planning. However, it is crucial that users are aware of the uncertainties associated with this information and ensure that these are appropriately considered within the decision-making process. It is assumed that users of the Threshold Detector are sufficiently informed about good practice in climate risk assessment to apply the code appropriately; climate risk assessment guidance is outside the scope of this user guide, although readers may wish to refer to the UKCP18 guidance

documents¹.

Single outcome versus range of outcomes: Climate model projections, such as those provided by UKCP18, should be interpreted as representing a range of possible futures. Natural climate variability is an important component of projected changes, and therefore any single projection offers only a limited representation of the range of possible outcomes. UKCP18 provides an ensemble of projections, allowing conditional probabilities of different outcomes to be inferred from the spread of projected changes. For example, Figure 3 illustrates projected changes in different threshold-crossing metrics associated with hot days in the London area (defined here as days when the daily maximum temperature exceeds 30 °C), calculated using the 16 ensemble members of UKCP18. While projections from individual ensemble members may differ substantially, the ensemble as a whole indicates a clear increase in all metrics, with an apparent acceleration after the 2040s.

Figure 3. Changes in hot days in the London area with daily tmax greater than 30 °C. Timeseries of a) the number of threshold exceedances per year, b) the number of threshold exceedance spells per year, and c) the length of the longest spell in a year computed with the 16 UKCP18 ensemble members (grey lines). The ensemble mean is represented by the dark red line.

Multi-model ensembles: In addition to internal climate variability, uncertainty also arises from inter-model differences. Where possible, it is preferable to consider multi-model ensembles, which account not only for natural variability but also for modelling uncertainty. In the case of UKCP18, in addition to the ensemble members derived from a single model, there are also four projections driven by boundary conditions from four different CMIP5 global climate models. More comprehensive assessments of the modelling uncertainty can be undertaken through the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) [4].

Near-term timescales: When assessing threshold-crossing changes in the near future, forecasts from seasonal or decadal prediction systems may have advantages, as they can, in principle, offer enhanced predictive skill associated with certain modes of variability, though it is possible that individual prediction systems may underestimate the full range of variability. Such skill is not present in the uninitialised projections of UKCP18, where

¹ <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/approach/collaboration/ukcp/guidance-reports>

changes are estimated for the general case, rather than for a specific realisation of natural variability. However, as predictive skill is generally limited to specific features and relatively short lead times, the use of uninitialised model projections is not deemed to constitute a major limitation in this context.

Bias correction: Finally, when observational datasets such as HadUK-Grid are available, they can help build confidence in model-based projections of threshold crossings by enabling simple evaluation assessments, as illustrated in Figure 4. The plots show the mean value, trend, and standard deviation of annual exceedances over the observational period, for both the ensemble members (blue bars) and the observational data (dark red line), for the example of hot days in London discussed above. In this example, UKCP18 projections appear to be broadly consistent with observations, although no bias correction was applied to the model data. However, when model biases are present, threshold-crossing estimates cannot be reliably derived without first applying bias correction to the model data, as common in impact studies [5]. While the Threshold Detector is not designed to perform bias correction (or, more precisely, bias adjustment), it can accept adjusted input data. Users are therefore encouraged to apply bias correction to their datasets where there is limited confidence that biases are negligible [6], while also recognising that different adjustment methods may themselves contribute additional uncertainty.

Figure 4. Hot days in the London area with daily tmax greater than 30 °C. The plots (left to right) show the mean, trend and standard deviation of the annual threshold exceedances during 1981-2004 estimated with the UKCP18 ensembles (blue bars) and HadUK-Grid observations (dark red line).

In conclusion, threshold-crossing projections need to be interpreted in the context of uncertainty arising from natural variability and model differences. The use of ensembles, evaluation against observations, and bias treatment, where appropriate, are important steps in ensuring robust results. With these considerations in mind, the Threshold Detector can provide meaningful insights into future changes in climate threshold crossings.

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